

Parametric study of a solid fluid air conditioning system

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we conducted a parametric study of the air-to-ground heat-conditioning system and used the air-to-ground heat exchanger or the Canadian well, which is an integrated cooling system with low energy consumption that exploits the geothermal inertia based on the experimental design method.

In this study, we want to study the effect of three factors and their interactions, thermal conductivity, tube diameter, and tube thickness, on temperature using a complete two-level factorial design to obtain a moderate temperature exit from the studied tube.

By conducting several experiments and after studying the validity of the model by comparing the experimental results with the results obtained from the equations, we found that increasing the value of the tube thickness and thermal conductivity while decreasing the value of the tube circle diameter, we reached a good efficiency of the studied model.

1 INTRODUCTION

In Algeria and in most countries of the world, the energy demand for air conditioning has increased very sharply, especially in recent years due to abnormally high temperatures due to increased pollution and gas emissions. To deal with this reality, several technologies have been developed, including the proposal to configure a small-scale power plant with a nominal electric production of 100 kW from a low-potential heat source, where the study revealed that it would be possible to generate electric power over the full range of the proposed temperature within the studied hypotheses. This work is considered as an alternative solution to reduce the consumption of non-renewable energy [1]. Other techniques to reduce the consumption of non-renewable energy that we are interested in studying in this work also include a heat exchanger between the air and the ground, also called the Canadian well.

A Canadian well consists of one or more buried tubes to supply buildings with air conditioning, in summer for cooling and in winter for heating. The principle of the system is to inject into the habitat a flow of air coming from the outside which is pre-forced to circulate in a tube buried deep in the ground.

Air-ground heat exchangers have been the subject of numerous studies, both numerical, and experimental. Numerical studies are based on different models. Among them:

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The thermal performance of the helical formation of earth-air heat exchanger (EAHE) intended for summer cooling, in the hot and arid regions of Algeria. An unstable 3D digital modelling of a new composition with different pitch spacing is performed [2], in this work; a study is presented on a ground-air heat exchanger for the cooling of buildings in the climatic conditions of the Algerian desert. Using a one-dimensional transient model, the influence of dynamic and geometric parameters on the thermal performance of the EAHE is studied [3], based on a numerical study based on a nodal approach, we carried out a numerical and parametric analysis of the vertical input and output parts of an air-soil heat exchanger. We note that the temperature variations are greater in the vertical input tube than in the vertical output tube. There is cooling of the air along the vertical input tube and heating along the vertical output tube [4], an optimum depth of 5 m was obtained for soil-air heat exchangers used in air conditioning applications in the Adrar region located in the Algerian desert based on the criterion of constant annual soil temperature using a specific MATLAB program. Then, EAHE was simulated using the climatic conditions of Adrar. The first model developed was validated using experimental data from the literature. Then, a parametric analysis was carried out to evaluate and study the effect of the length of the buried tube and the air flow rate on the air temperature at the exit of the tube [5], ANSYS-CFX® was used to simulate the EAHE transient functioning during heating and cooling operation modes, and to numerically assess the influence of different design parameters and operation conditions on the outlet air temperature and soil-air heat transfer rate, namely the distance between parallel pipes, pipes diameter and airflow velocity. The numerical predictions were compared with previously obtained analytical results and validated against experimental data. Once validated, the numerical model was used to perform a parametric assessment on the effect of three different pipe diameters operating with different air velocities, and the effect of three distances between adjacent pipes operating with different air velocities and pipe diameters [6], This paper presented numerical results for the thermal behavior of EAHE installations, considering three sites (named FURG, IF, and PN) located in the south Brazilian coastal city of Rio Grande. The work counted on in situ data obtained from standard penetration tests made in the city, which allowed to estimate the soil profiles for the sites under study. Moreover, the temperatures of the air and of the soil surface were more realistically described using weather data from an international source, which was incorporated in the numerical model. Besides, the influence of water table was regarded in all soil thermo-physical properties. Such methodology helped to raise more reliable prospects for EAHE installations in the region [7], in the researcher's paper; he studied the combination of two technologies of the ground-to-air heat exchanger and solar chimney that are two renewable energy technologies. The first technology relies on geothermal energy sources and the second on solar energy to meet the requirements of thermal comfort, especially in arid regions and in winter. The new idea was to combine the two technologies in the same body, using a PVC pipe that acts as a solar chimney at the outlet of the system. For this purpose, thermal insulation of the inlet pipe is applied, while the outlet is directly exposed to external climatic conditions (sun, wind) to create solar chimney effects through the buoyancy effect. The system was completely passive with zero power consumption [8], this study proposed by the researcher aims to compare the performance parameters of a horizontal T-shaped EAHE and a vertical 3U-shaped EAHE, with a conventional horizontal EAHE. A validated and validated numerical model was used to evaluate the thermal potential. At the same time analytical methods were used to arrive at the occupied soil volume by fitting EAHE and air flow head losses [9], this paper presents an investigation on the heating performance and operating feasibility of two EAHEs in three different geo-climatic regions in Algeria. First, the performances of the EAHEs were experimentally studied in the temperate Oran climate and the corresponding results were used for validation of the numerical part. The experiment allowed to analyze the effect of the pipe material on the performance of the two EAHEs that are made of different materials (PVC and Zinc). After validation of the numerical part, the study was extended to three different climates including a temperate climate for Oran, an arid climate for Bechar and a steppe climate for El-Bayadh cities. For these climates, the heating study is rarely considered in this context. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis was conducted in order to evaluate the operating feasibility of the EAHEs in the considered regions [10], In this study, the initial conditions of the problem are obtained and the temperature equation specified model is solved analytically, by considering that the vertical part of an EAHE or a vertical EAHE is under periodic fluctuations in both ambient air temperature and soil temperature. The model can predict the air temperature variation along vertical and horizontal section of the tube for any hour of the day and can be used for a vertical EAHE. It can also determine the daily or annually mean and amplitude of the total cooling or heating effect of the tube [11], the present paper is focused on the geometric evaluation of several earth-air heat exchangers arrangements according to the Constructural Design method. The performance indicators are the minimization of its soil volume occupation, the minimization of its airflow pressure drop, and the maximization of its thermal potential [12].

This study will allow us to understand the evolution of the air temperature when it leaves the exchanger according to the thickness and diameter of the tube, as well as in terms of thermal conductivity. We will also evaluate the evolution of the thermal efficiency of the system through the experimental design method.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

We have represented the geometry of the air-ground exchanger in 2D, as shown in the figure below:

Fig. 1 – illustrator image of the air-ground exchanger

In this work, we tested a ground-to-air heat exchanger as shown in Figure 1, with a maximum vertical depth of 5 meters, a maximum length of a horizontal tube placed in the bedrock of 15 m, and two 90-degree elbows. We used a complete factorial design of 2^3 , meaning 8 trials were obtained. We changed the values of the factors to study their effect on the temperature that comes out of the ground-air heat exchanger, and their values were determined according to each experiment, so that the first factor was the diameter of the tube with a value between 10 and 14 centimetres, and the second factor was the thickness of the tube with a value between 2 and 5 millimetres, as well as the factor The third is the thermal conductivity of the soil. We change its value between 0.04 and 0.33 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. In the table below displays the matrix of the resulting experiments:

Table 1 - Theoretical matrix of experiments

Factors				The final result
Exp(i)	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	pipe diameter(cm)	Pipe thickness(mm)	Temperature
1	0.04	10	2	21.3
2	0.33	10	2	25
3	0.04	14	2	26
4	0.33	14	2	22.8
5	0.04	10	5	20
6	0.33	10	5	23.5
7	0.04	14	5	23
8	0.33	14	5	22

3 Experimental design and statistical analysis

There are several ways to study the effect of several factors on response, and one of the most common methods is to change one factor while keeping the other factors constant. A factor to determine the experimental field so that the level +1 is the maximum value and -1 is the minimum value. As a work step, these tests to be performed are represented in the form of a matrix. In our work, we chose the effect of 3 factors: Thermal conductivity (X_1), pipe diameter(X_2), Pipethickness(X_3) on the response: Temperature (Y) so that the resulting full tax level becomes $2^3 = 8$ experiments for this design, where 2 represent the two values extremes of the factors and 3 represents the number of factors in the table below displaying the matrix of the resulting experiments.

The model with second-order interactions takes into account the interaction between each factor and another. The effects of the interactions are measured and represented by the coefficients a_{ij} in equation 1:

$$y = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k x_i a_i + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^k I_{ij} x_i x_j \tag{1}$$

The postulated mathematical model is written in this case in the following form:

$$y = a_0 + a_1 x_{i1} + a_2 x_{i2} + a_3 x_{i3} + I_{12} x_{i1} x_{i2} + I_{13} x_{i1} x_{i3} + I_{23} x_{i2} x_{i3} + e_i \tag{2}$$

In this study, we represent a polynomial model in Equation 2 in the form of matrices through the 8 experiments conducted in the work:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \\ y_5 \\ y_6 \\ y_7 \\ y_8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & x_{1.1} & x_{1.2} & x_{1.3} & x_{1.1} \cdot x_{1.2} & x_{1.1} \cdot x_{1.3} & x_{1.2} \cdot x_{1.3} \\ 1 & x_{2.1} & x_{2.2} & x_{2.3} & x_{2.1} \cdot x_{2.2} & x_{2.1} \cdot x_{2.3} & x_{2.2} \cdot x_{2.3} \\ 1 & x_{3.1} & x_{3.2} & x_{3.3} & x_{3.1} \cdot x_{3.2} & x_{3.1} \cdot x_{3.3} & x_{3.2} \cdot x_{3.3} \\ 1 & x_{4.1} & x_{4.2} & x_{4.3} & x_{4.1} \cdot x_{4.2} & x_{4.1} \cdot x_{4.3} & x_{4.2} \cdot x_{4.3} \\ 1 & x_{5.1} & x_{5.2} & x_{5.3} & x_{5.1} \cdot x_{5.2} & x_{5.1} \cdot x_{5.3} & x_{5.2} \cdot x_{5.3} \\ 1 & x_{6.1} & x_{6.2} & x_{6.3} & x_{6.1} \cdot x_{6.2} & x_{6.1} \cdot x_{6.3} & x_{6.2} \cdot x_{6.3} \\ 1 & x_{7.1} & x_{7.2} & x_{7.3} & x_{7.1} \cdot x_{7.2} & x_{7.1} \cdot x_{7.3} & x_{7.2} \cdot x_{7.3} \\ 1 & x_{8.1} & x_{8.2} & x_{8.3} & x_{8.1} \cdot x_{8.2} & x_{8.1} \cdot x_{8.3} & x_{8.2} \cdot x_{8.3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ I_{12} \\ I_{13} \\ I_{23} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_3 \\ e_4 \\ e_5 \\ e_6 \\ e_7 \\ e_8 \end{pmatrix} \tag{3}$$

Where the values of the coefficients can be determined as per Eq. (4):

$$Coefficients = ({}^t X X)^{-1} ({}^t X)(Y) \tag{4}$$

Table 2 - Matrix of Experiments

Factors				The final result
Exp(i)	Thermal conductivity (W.m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	pipe diameter(cm)	Pipe thickness(mm)	Temperature
1	-1	-1	-1	21.3
2	1	-1	-1	25
3	-1	1	-1	26
4	1	1	-1	22.8
5	-1	-1	1	20
6	1	-1	1	23.5
7	-1	1	1	23
8	1	1	1	22

The equation 5 shows the complete mathematical model:

$$\hat{Y} = 22.95 + 0.375X_1 + 0.5X_2 + 0.825X_3 - 1.425X_1X_2 + 0.25X_1X_3 - 0.125X_2X_3 + 0.3X_1X_2X_3 \quad (5)$$

To determine the significance of the various effects, we use the Student test.

In order to be able to conduct the static student test, we choose to delete the last term of the complete model (the highest order interaction) to avoid the case or the denominator n-p=0. The new model to consider is:

$$\hat{Y} = 22.95 + 0.375X_1 + 0.5X_2 + 0.825X_3 - 1.425X_1X_2 + 0.25X_1X_3 - 0.125X_2X_3 \quad (6)$$

4 The tests for significance

To calculate the variance of our S^2 deviations we have the experimentally measured values Y_i and we calculate the estimated responses \hat{Y}_i in model 4 and the residuals represented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Results of estimated responses and squared deviations

Exp (i)	Y_i	\hat{Y}_i	$(Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2$	$(\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2$
1	21.3	21.6	0.09	1.8225
2	25	24.7	0.09	3.0625
3	26	25.7	0.09	7.5625
4	22.8	23.1	0.09	0.0225
5	20	19.7	0.09	10.5625
6	23.5	23.8	0.09	0.7225
7	23	23.3	0.09	0.1225
8	22	21.7	0.09	1.5625
			$\sum (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 = 0.72$	$\sum (\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2 = 25.44$

The statistical calculations used to determine the standard deviation S_i involve the variance of the deviations (the differences between the experimental values Y_i and the estimated values predicted by the model \hat{Y}_i^2) according to the equation:

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^8 (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n - p} = \frac{0.72}{8 - 7} = 0.72 \tag{7}$$

The values of S_i will be:

$$S_0 = S_1 = S_2 = S_3 = S_{12} = S_{13} = S_{23} = \sqrt{\frac{S^2}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.72}{8}} = 0.3 \tag{8}$$

The value of t_{crit} for a risk $\alpha=0.4$ and a degree of freedom $ddl= n-p=8-7$ and taken from the student table $t_{crit} = t(0.4,1) = 1.376$

Finally we calculate the values to test:

$$t_i = \frac{a_i}{S_i} \tag{9}$$

And we compare their absolute values to t_{crit} in the table to make a decision about the significance of the factor effects and their interactions.

Table 4 - Significance Results

Effect	a _i	S _i	t _i	t _i ≥ t _{crit} ?	a _i s significant
a ₀	22.95	0.3	76.5	Yes	Significant
a ₁	0.375	0.3	1.25	No	Not significant
a ₂	0.5	0.3	1.66	Yes	Significant
a ₃	-0.825	0.3	-2.75	Yes	Significant
I ₁₂	-1.425	0.3	-4.75	Yes	Significant
I ₁₃	0.25	0.3	0.83	No	Not significant
I ₂₃	-0.125	0.3	-0.41	No	Not significant

According to Table 4, the thermal conductivity coefficient a₁ and the interaction of thermal conductivity with the thickness of the I₁₃ pipe and the diameter of the pipe with the thickness of the pipe I₂₃ have a small effect (considered = 0), as for the coefficient of pipe diameter a₂ and the thickness of the pipe a₃ and the interaction of thermal conductivity with pipe diameter I₁₂ is important and they have an impact on the result obtained, meaning that their effect is not equal to 0.

4.1 Model Validation

Table 5: Analysis of variance

Variation	sum of squares	ddl	medium square	F _{cal}
Connection	25.44	7-1	4.24	5.88
Residues	0.72	8-7	0.72	
Total	26.16	8-1	3.73	

By performing a contrast analysis (ANOVA) and calculating various statistical norms, one can study the validity of the model obtained with a risk (α = 0.4) as well as a quality study in terms of agreement with measured data and its ability to predict and accurate enough. To test the validity of the model obtained, we have created table 4.3 to analyze the variance of the study. According to the results obtained, F_{cal} is compared to F_{crit}. F_{crit} is obtained from the Fisher table for the parameters α = 0.4, dll₁ = p - 1 and dll₂ = n - p (F_{crit}(0.4, 6, 1) = 3.27). F_{cal} > F_{crit} so the regression model is valid.

4.1.1 Coefficient of determination

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} = \frac{25.44}{26.16} = 0.9724 \tag{10}$$

By calculating the coefficient of determination R² in order to prove that the quality of the model and according to the results obtained is close to 1, and this indicates that the model is very good with regard to its compatibility with the observed data.

Calculate Adequate Accuracy from Equation 11:

$$Acc_{adeq} = \frac{\max(\hat{y}) - \min(\hat{y})}{\sqrt{\frac{p * \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}}} \quad (11)$$

$$Acc_{adeq} = \frac{\max(21.6, 24.7, 25.7, 23.1, 19.7, 23.8, 23.3, 21.7) - \min(21.6, 24.7, 25.7, 23.1, 19.7, 23.8, 23.3, 21.7)}{\sqrt{\frac{7 * 0.72}{8}}} = 7.559 \quad (12)$$

$Acc_{adeq} = 7.559 > 4$ the model has adequate good precision.

5 HENRY'S LINE OF RESIDUAL VALUES

The Henry's line is a graphical method used for checking the normality of the data. The residue represents the difference between experimental and the predicted value of the regression. If the points are near a straight line it is said that the data is distributed normally. Henry's lines are useful for evaluating the normality of a data file, even when the number of observations is quite low [13].

The graph 2 represents the relationship between the actual experimental response values versus the expected response values calculated from the model through what the graph shows. It shows that the correlation is excellent between the temperature obtained experimentally and those that can be predicted through the mathematical relationship proposed in the equation mentioned above. Thus, we can conclude that the model correctly predicts the temperature depending on the factors that we have chosen in experience.

Fig. 2 – Linear correlation between the ratio of calculated and observed temperature

5.1 Plots of influence graphs

Through the graphs of the effects of factors and interactions on temperature, one can study the factors that have a direct impact on the experiment, after having studied the effectiveness of the model and checked its quality.

5.1.1 Main effects plots

Fig. 3 – Graphical representation of the main effects thermal conductivity and pipe diameter and pipe thickness

In the three graphs obtained from the experiment for the effect of thermal conductivity, pipe diameter and pipe thickness in Figure 3, we conclude that all factors have general effects on temperature, so we conclude that the effect of pipe thickness is negative (using an increase in pipe thickness the temperature decreases and vice versa).

On the other hand, the thermal conductivity and the diameter of the tube show a generally positive effect (by increasing the thermal conductivity and the diameter of the tube, we see that the temperature increases).

We also note that the effect of pipe thickness is slightly greater than the effect of pipe diameter and thermal conductivity on temperature.

5.1.2 Graphs of interaction effects

Fig. 4 – Graphical representation of the interaction effects

Figure 4 shows the results obtained from the interactions. For the interaction of thermal conductivity with tube diameter I_{12} , data for the average response of thermal conductivity factor a_1 for two levels of factor tube diameter a_2 . The two lines in the graph are not parallel, and the obtained results show that the effect of the thermal conductivity factor was more reactive than the effect of pipe diameter in terms of their interaction with each other on the temperature. Regarding the effect of the reactants between I_{13} , it was found that the thermal conductivity factor had the most influence on the pipe thickness factor, and with respect to I_{23} , its results showed that the effect of pipe diameter was more effective in its interaction between it and the pipe thickness.

6 CONCLUSION

The energy conservation is considered the biggest challenge facing the contemporary world, especially renewable energy or energy that does not cost large sums of money and maintains a purer environment when exploited. This study, as it represents a numerical simulation of the heat exchanger with natural and 100% free energy, yielded very stimulating results to continue this research, which were as follows:

- The heat input model was subjected to an ANOVA test which proved that the model is accurate, reliable and can be useful in predicting other outcomes in the area of study.
- Through three factors we tested and according to the graphs we obtained, it was found that increasing the thickness of the tube helped reduce the temperature, while increasing the tube diameter factor and the thermal conductivity factor did not help reduce the temperature.
- With regard to the interaction that occurred between the factors that we studied, we concluded that the interaction between the thermal conductivity factor and the pipe diameter factor has a direct effect on the temperature, unlike other interactions that were not significantly affected.
- The study of a ground-air heat exchanger using the experimental design method is very important and needs more in-depth and research because it provides us with high quality results that help us as researchers.

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